

MANUAL For

PARENTAL DECISION MAKING SCALE FOR PRIVATE TUITION

PDMSPT – JKS

Dr. SANJEEV KUMAR JHA

Former Consultant
Educational Survey Division
National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT)
NEW DELHI

NATIONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CORPORATION, AGRA

Manual for

Parental Decision-Making Scale for Private Tuition (PDMSPT)

Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Jha
UGC-NET, M.Sc. (Mathematics), MA (Sociology), M.Ed. and Ph.D. (Education)

Krjhasanjeev03@gmail.com, and <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5015-038X>

Former Consultant, Educational Survey Division,
National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT), New
Delhi-110016

Citation (APA 7th Edition)

Jha, S. K. (2026). *Parental decision-making scale for private tuition* [Psychological test]. National Psychological Corporation.

Introduction

Private tuition, metaphorically termed ‘shadow education’ (Bray, 1999), has become a defining feature of modern educational systems worldwide. Originating as a niche practice in Asia, where countries like Japan, South Korea, and Singapore institutionalized private tutoring as a supplement to formal schooling (Kinyaduka, 2014; Matsuoka, 2015). It has now emerged as a global trend. Countries across Europe, North America, and the Global South have witnessed a remarkable surge in the prevalence of private tuition, reflecting a universal parental aspiration for academic excellence (Davies, 2004; Kumar & Chowdhury, 2021).

India with its diverse population and competitive education system, exemplifies the exponential growth of this phenomenon. Private tuition has rooted itself deeply within the Indian education landscape, fuelled by the desire to secure higher academic outcomes and better career prospects for children (Sujatha, 2014; Jha, 2023). According to the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO, 2016), approximately 25% of Indian students (one in every four) are enrolled in private tuition, underscoring its growing significance as a parallel education system.

Drivers of the Private Tuition in India

The Indian context presents a unique interplay of cultural, economic, and systemic factors that have catalyzed the demand for private tuition. Several interrelated dynamics contribute to its prevalence:

1. **High-Stakes Academic Environment:** Competition to get admission in prestigious educational institution (IIT/ AIIMS, etc) as these institutions have for limited seats is high. The specialized coaching centers, promising exam-oriented preparation and tailored strategies, have mushroomed across urban and semi-urban areas, creating an industry worth billions of rupees (ASSOCHAM, 2013; Dongre & Tewary, 2015).
2. **Inconsistencies in Public Education Quality:** The quality of public schooling in India remains uneven (Sujatha, 2014). Private tuition emerges as a vital recourse for parents seeking to bridge these gaps and ensure their children’s academic competence (Jha, 2023; Kumar & Chowdhury, 2021).

3. **Parental Expectations and Cultural Norms:** Parents, driven by a strong belief in education as a vehicle for upward mobility, are willing to allocate substantial portions of their income to private tutoring. This commitment stems from societal pressures and the conviction that additional academic support is critical for their children to outperform peers (Sharma, 2024).
4. **Perceived Limitations of Mainstream Schooling:** The lack of personalized attention in conventional schools, exacerbated by high student-teacher ratios, drives many parents to seek individualized tutoring solutions. Private tuition, with its promise of tailored pedagogy, becomes an attractive alternative for addressing diverse learning needs (Basu, 2014).

Socio-Economic Implications

Now, Private tuition is a multi-billion US dollar market in India (Jha, 2023). Thus, it has the significant socio-economic implications on affordability of the family. Thus, it accentuates educational disparities. Affluent families can afford premium-quality tutoring, while economically weaker sections struggle to access basic support. This duality perpetuates socio-economic inequalities, as academic success increasingly hinges on financial capacity rather than merit (Bray, 2009).

Furthermore, the dependence on private tuition poses challenges for policymakers striving to create an equitable education system. It raises pressing questions about the adequacy of mainstream schooling and the unintended consequences of an over-reliance on supplemental education (Dongre & Tewary, 2015).

Parental Decision-Making

Researches are exploring the underlying factors influencing parental decisions to invest in private tuition, particularly in the Indian context, remains limited (Bhokar & Bray, 2018). Parental decisions are complex, shaped by an intricate web of beliefs, societal norms, and perceived constraints. To unravel these motivations, it is essential to employ a robust theoretical framework that can capture the multifaceted nature of these choices.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour: A Theoretical Lens for Scale

The increasing reliance on private tuition (PT) has become a global phenomenon. It is influenced by high-stakes competitive exams, peer influence, societal norms, and perceived inadequacies within mainstream school systems (Sujatha, 2014; Jha, 2024). Studies suggest that PT is often associated with enhanced academic performance (Rocha & Hamed, 2018). However, the decision-making process for opting private tuition is complex and multidimensional.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) provides a robust framework for exploring the parental decision-making process regarding PT. Ajzen (1991) in TPB posits that behaviour is primarily guided by intentions, which are influenced by three critical components: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. This framework has been effectively applied to various contexts, including private tuition, as demonstrated in studies such as Abu-Shawish (2023) and Byun and Park (2012).

Each component of TPB offers valuable insights into the psychological and social mechanisms that shape the intention to enrol a child in private tuition:

1. Attitude: parental attitudes towards PT are shaped by their beliefs about its effectiveness, such as academic success for their child. A favourable attitude, such as perceiving PT as indispensable for better academic performance, directly correlates with a stronger intention to opt for these services.

2. Subjective Norms: parents are often influenced by the expectations of family members, peers, or the broader community. If the majority of parents in a community enrol their children in PT then it acts as social expectations. Thus, the degree to which parents internalize these social norms significantly affects their decision-making process.

3. Perceived Behavioural Control: enrolling in PT may depend on factors such as financial resources, availability of time, or access to skilled tutors. Higher perceived control, such as financial stability or the proximity of quality tutoring services, increases the likelihood of acting on the intention to arrange tuition.

4. Intention: parents with a positive attitude towards private tuition, strong social support from peers, and adequate resources are more likely to translate their intention into action by enrolling their child in private tuition.

Objectives of the Parental Decision-Making Scale

In order to understand the parental Decision-Making for private tuition, this scale has been developed. The scale identifies and measures the factors influencing the decision to opt for PT.

Sample Selection

A purposive sampling technique was utilized to select a sample of 304 parents of school-aged children. This method was chosen for its ability to intentionally target individuals directly involved in decision-making processes related to private tuition. Purposive sampling is particularly effective in studies requiring focused insights from specific subpopulations. This size provides an adequate balance between feasibility and the statistical power needed for robust data analysis.

Characteristics of Children of the sample

Table-1: Characteristics of Children of the Sample

		Frequency	Per cent	Cumulative Per cent
Gender	Boy	162	53.3	53.3
	Girl	142	46.7	100.0
Take Private Tuition	Yes	156	51.3	51.3
	No	148	48.7	100
Caste	General	154	50.7	50.7
	SC	39	12.8	63.5
	ST	24	7.9	71.4
	OBC	87	28.6	100.0
Socio Economic Status	Low	51	16.8	16.8
	Average	231	76.0	92.8
	High	22	7.2	100.0

Research Design and Data Collection

A cross-sectional survey design was employed to collect relevant data. Data was collected using an online survey platform (Google Forms) as the primary tool for data collection. Further, Google Forms as it was considered effective in such cases (Wright, 2005).

Description of the Scale

Table-2: Descriptive Statistics of the Scale (N=304)

Item Sl. No.	Item	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
1.	Private tuition improves academic performance of my child.	1	5	3.44	1.088
2.	Private tuition is necessary for my child's success.	1	5	3.10	1.183
3.	Private tuition provides personalized attention.	1	5	3.47	1.087
4.	The advantages of private tuition surpass the expenses.	1	5	3.47	1.065
5.	Private tuition helps gain confidence in learning.	1	5	3.44	1.142

6.	Other parents in my community send their children to private tuition.	1	5	3.91	.891
7.	My family members think I should enroll my child in private tuition.	1	5	3.23	1.102
8.	Teachers recommend private tuition for my child.	1	5	2.56	1.136
9.	My child's friends attend private tuition.	1	5	3.72	.971
10.	I feel pressure from society to arrange private tuition for my child.	1	5	2.73	1.212
11.	I can afford to private tuition for my child.	1	5	3.57	1.028
12.	I can easily arrange transportation for my child to attend private tuition.	1	5	3.16	1.149
13.	I have enough time to manage my child's schedule, including private tuition.	1	5	3.04	1.137
14.	There are enough private tuition options available in my area.	1	5	3.38	1.197
15.	I am confident that private tuition will fit into my child's routine.	1	5	3.10	1.193
16.	I plan to enroll my child in private tuition in the near future.	1	5	3.23	1.113
17.	I am willing to prioritize private tuition over other extracurricular activities.	1	5	2.91	1.115
18.	I am likely to recommend private tuition to other parents.	1	5	2.80	1.095
19.	I would continue private tuition even if my child's school performance improves.	1	5	3.09	1.254
20.	I intend to increase the number of private tuition hours if needed.	1	5	2.94	1.183

Application of the Scale

The scale is designed to study parental decision-making regarding private tuition. It has been developed specifically for parents of school-going children. Therefore, it is applicable to parents whose children are currently enrolled in school and are in the process of deciding whether to arrange private tuition for their wards.

Development of the Parental Decision-Making Scale for Private Tuition

Step-1: Literature Review and Items Writing

A comprehensive review of the literature was conducted to establish a robust theoretical foundation, with the Theory of Planned Behaviour serving as the primary framework. Drawing from this theory and insights from existing literature, a pool of 20 items was systematically developed. The items were discussed with experts.

Step-2: Selection of Items

For this purpose items analysis was conducted. Item analysis is a fundamental procedure for evaluating the performance of every item in a psychometric test. It makes clear which items most influence the overall test result.

Table-3: Item-Total Statistics

Item Sl. No.	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Decision
1.	60.87	158.379	.704	.896	Retained
2.	61.21	155.650	.739	.895	Retained
3.	60.84	160.492	.624	.898	Retained
4.	60.84	166.406	.412	.904	Retained
5.	60.87	158.374	.667	.897	Retained
6.	60.40	170.821	.311	.905	Retained
7.	61.08	161.591	.573	.900	Retained
8.	61.75	163.952	.468	.902	Retained
9.	60.59	170.539	.291	.906	Retained
10.	61.58	167.988	.299	.907	Retained
11.	60.74	169.548	.308	.906	Retained
12.	61.14	167.728	.330	.906	Retained
13.	61.27	164.732	.440	.903	Retained

14.	60.92	166.882	.341	.906	Retained
15.	61.21	156.629	.697	.896	Retained
16.	61.08	158.333	.688	.897	Retained
17.	61.40	158.372	.686	.897	Retained
18.	61.51	157.492	.734	.895	Retained
19.	61.22	154.608	.727	.895	Retained
20.	61.37	155.955	.728	.895	Retained

In this scale item-total correlations (Biserial Correlation) was calculated with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The items having more item-total correlation more than 0.2 were retained in the final scale. This further helps in maintaining the validity and reliability of the scale.

Step-3 Finalization of the Scale

Factor analysis using the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method was conducted. This technique identifies underlying dimensions by summarizing the variance in observed variables into fewer components, ensuring they capture the maximum shared variance.

Communalities and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy

The KMO value (0.900, see table 4) is considered “marvellous” according to Kaiser’s classification, suggesting that the sample size and data are highly suitable for factor analysis. Furthermore, for Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity, a significant result indicates that the data has sufficient correlations to justify the application of factor analysis (Table 4).

Table-4: Communalities and KMO and Bartlett's Test

Item Sl. No.	Initial	Extraction
1.	1.000	.734
2.	1.000	.720
3.	1.000	.695
4.	1.000	.411

5.	1.000	.709
6.	1.000	.629
7.	1.000	.549
8.	1.000	.595
9.	1.000	.648
10.	1.000	.702
11.	1.000	.638
12.	1.000	.662
13.	1.000	.609
14.	1.000	.537
15.	1.000	.657
16.	1.000	.611
17.	1.000	.638
18.	1.000	.672
19.	1.000	.683
20.	1.000	.724
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.900
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3236.783
	Df	190
	Sig.	.000
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Communalities represent the proportion of variance in each variable that can be explained by the extracted factors. Initial communalities are all set to 1, indicating the total variance in the variable. The extracted communalities show the variance explained by the retained factors after extraction.

Total Variance Explained

Table-5: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.692	38.461	38.461	7.692	38.461	38.461	6.140	30.700	30.700
2	2.310	11.549	50.010	2.310	11.549	50.010	2.918	14.589	45.289
3	1.689	8.447	58.457	1.689	8.447	58.457	2.202	11.011	56.300
4	1.135	5.675	64.131	1.135	5.675	64.131	1.566	7.831	64.131
5	.860	4.300	68.432						

6	.764	3.822	72.254						
7	.695	3.473	75.726						
8	.636	3.180	78.907						
9	.601	3.005	81.911						
10	.501	2.505	84.417						
11	.453	2.266	86.683						
12	.413	2.063	88.746						
13	.389	1.943	90.689						
14	.357	1.787	92.477						
15	.322	1.609	94.086						
16	.287	1.437	95.523						
17	.256	1.282	96.805						
18	.241	1.205	98.009						
19	.207	1.036	99.046						
20	.191	.954	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

The total variance table shows the number of components extracted, their eigenvalues, and the percentage of variance explained. Four components were extracted, explaining a cumulative 64.131% of the variance.

Rotated Component Matrix

The rotated matrix provides a clearer grouping of variables into components by redistributing the variance to achieve simpler and more interpretable factor structures.

Table-6: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Item Sl. No.	Component			
	1	2	3	4
1.	.844			
2.	.809			
3.	.779			
4.	.608			
5.	.833			
6.				.752
7.	.507			
8.			.707	
9.				.764
10.			.794	
11.		.750		
12.		.802		
13.		.751		
14.		.724		
15.	.567	.		
16.	.686			
17.	.603			
18.	.699			
19.	.725			
20.	.739			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.				
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				
a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.				

Dimensions of the Scale

Considering factor loading, the items were classified component wise.

Table-7: Components and Factor Loadings

Component	Items Included	Factor Loadings
Component 1: Perceived Benefits of Private Tuition	Private tuition improves academic performance of my child.	0.844
	Private tuition is necessary for my child's success.	0.809
	Private tuition provides personalized attention.	0.779
	The advantages of private tuition surpass the expenses.	0.608
	Private tuition helps gain confidence in learning.	0.833
	My family members think I should enroll my child in private tuition.	0.507
	I am confident that private tuition will fit into my child's routine.	0.567
	I plan to enroll my child in private tuition in the near future.	0.686
	I am willing to prioritize private tuition over other extracurricular activities.	0.603
	I am likely to recommend private tuition to other parents.	0.699
	I would continue private tuition even if my child's school performance improves.	0.725
	I intend to increase the number of private tuition hours if needed.	0.739
Component 2: Feasibility of Private Tuition	I can afford to private tuition for my child.	0.750
	I can easily arrange transportation for my child to attend private tuition.	0.802
	I have enough time to manage my child's schedule, including private tuition.	0.751
	There are enough private tuition options available in my area.	0.724
Component 3 (3 & 4): Social Influence on Private Tuition	Teachers recommend private tuition for my child.	0.707
	I feel pressure from society to arrange private tuition for my child.	0.794
	Other parents in my community send their children to private tuition.	0.752
	My child's friends attend private tuition.	0.764

Rationale for Merging Components:

Component-3 and Component-4 had only two items each. Thus these components were merged to a single component. Field (2013) discusses factor analysis and PCA, including when it is appropriate to combine factors based on conceptual and statistical reasoning.

1. **Conceptual Overlap:** Component 3 (External Influence) and Component 4 includes items related to external or peer influence on parental decision-making for private tuition. Both components reflect the influence of external factors (whether from authority figures like teachers or from social networks), so they are conceptually related. Therefore, it is reasonable to merge them into a single component.
2. **Limited Number of Items:** Component 3 and Component 4 have only 2 items each. Components with too few items may not represent a reliable construct on their own and might benefit from merging with a closely related component to ensure robustness and reliability in the scale. Thus, merging these components helps to create a more stable and interpretable factor structure, especially in the context of scale development.
3. **Factor Loading:** The factor loadings for both components are above the threshold (e.g., 0.5), suggesting that the items have significant loadings on their respective components. However, combining them into a single dimension may help in reducing the number of components without losing meaningful information, improving interpretability, and simplifying the scale.

Thus, component 3 and component 4 are merged.

Validity of the Scale

The items in the scale were based on a strong theoretical framework. Thus, scale provides a valid data. Nevertheless, following validity aspects were established for the scale.

1. **Content Validity:** The items included in the tool represent key areas related to private tuition—such as perceived benefits, feasibility, and social influences.

These dimensions are based on theoretical constructs and expert judgment, ensuring that the tool covers the relevant aspects of parental decisions about private tuition. The items were also discussed with subject matter experts in the development process. It would further strengthen content validity.

2. **Construct Validity:** The factor analysis performed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) supports the tool’s construct validity. The factor structure identifies three meaningful components: *Perceived Benefits of Private Tuition*, *Feasibility of Private Tuition*, and *Social Influence on Private Tuition*. Each component groups related items with high factor loadings, which indicates that the tool accurately measures the underlying constructs it is intended to assess.
3. **Face Validity:** The items and dimensions included in the tool appear relevant and appropriate to the intended purpose of understanding parental perceptions of private tuition. This is evident from the alignment between the questions asked and the expected areas of influence on private tuition decisions.

Reliability

Table-8: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach’s Alpha	Cronbach’s Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.905	.903	20

Scoring Procedure

The tool uses a Likert-type scale for scoring, where respondents rate each of the 20 items on a 5-point scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Higher scores indicate stronger agreement with the statements regarding private tuition. The individual item responses are summed to generate a composite score, reflecting the overall perception of private tuition. Higher total scores suggest more favourable views toward private tuition, with a higher score indicating a greater likelihood of deciding in favour of enrolling in private tuition.

Table-9: Scoring for Each Item

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

Interpretation of Score

Descriptive Statistics

Table-10: Descriptive Statistics

N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
304	23	100	64.31	13.374

Z-score Norms

On the basis of statistical results z-score norms have been developed as represented in table 13. Norms for interpretation parental decision-making is given in the table 12.

Table-11: Z-Score for Parental Decision-Making on Private Tuition

Mean =64.31, SD=13.374, N=304

Raw Score	Z-Score	Raw Score	Z-Score
35	-2.19	65	0.05
36	-2.12	66	0.13
37	-2.04	67	0.20
38	-1.97	68	0.28
39	-1.89	69	0.35
40	-1.82	70	0.43
41	-1.74	71	0.50
42	-1.67	72	0.57
43	-1.59	73	0.65
44	-1.52	74	0.72
45	-1.44	75	0.80
46	-1.37	76	0.87
47	-1.29	77	0.95
48	-1.22	78	1.02
49	-1.14	79	1.10
50	-1.07	80	1.17
51	-1.00	81	1.25
52	-0.92	82	1.32
53	-0.85	83	1.40
54	-0.77	84	1.47
55	-0.70	85	1.55
56	-0.62	86	1.62
57	-0.55	87	1.70
58	-0.47	88	1.77
59	-0.40	89	1.85
60	-0.32	90	1.92
61	-0.25	91	2.00

62	-0.17	92	2.07
63	-0.10	93	2.15
64	-0.02	94	2.22

Table-12: Norms for Interpretation PDMPT

<i>Sl. No.</i>	<i>Z-Score</i>	<i>Grade</i>	<i>Decision-Making</i>
1.	+ 2.01 & above	A	Highly Decisive
2.	+ 1.26 to + 2.00	B	Decisive
3.	+ 0.51 to + 1.25	C	Strongly Inclined
4.	- 0.50 to + 0.50	D	Neutral
5.	- 0.51 to - 1.25	E	Reluctant
6.	- 1.26 to - 2.00	F	Highly Reluctant
7.	- 2.01 & below	G	Indecisive

Interpretation of the Decision

Highly Decisive

Highly decisive parents exhibit a strong and firm commitment toward enrolling their children in private tuition. They strongly perceive private tuition as beneficial for academic improvement, confidence building. They also consider private tuition as supportive role in long-term success of their children. These parents report high feasibility in terms of affordability of private tuition and they can manage time for it. Their decision in this regards minimally influenced by uncertainty or constraints. Their responses reflect a clear intention not only to enroll but also to continue or increase private tuition, if required.

Decisive

Decisive parents demonstrate a clear and positive orientation toward enrolling private tuition. They acknowledge its academic and personal benefits. Generally, they are in state to enrol their children in private tuition. Although minor concerns may exist, these do not significantly hinder their decision in this regard. Overall, such parents are likely to take concrete steps toward enrolling their child in private tuition.

Strongly Inclined

Parents in the strongly inclined category show a positive attitude toward enrolling their children to private tuition. But they have not yet reached a final decision. They recognize its potential benefits and are moderately confident about managing practical aspects such as cost and time. However, their decision remains conditional, often dependent on future academic needs or additional guidance from teachers or peers.

Neutral

Neutral parents neither clearly support nor oppose private tuition. Their responses indicate mixed perceptions regarding its benefits and feasibility, along with limited influence from social factors. These parents do not show a clear intention to enroll their children to private tuition. They may remain undecided unless it does not change progress of their children.

Highly Reluctant

Parents identified as highly reluctant express a strong resistance toward enrolling their children to private tuition. They tend to question its effectiveness, necessity, or value in relation to the cost and effort involved, including time. They have feasibility concerns and a low exposure to social pressure. These reinforce their reluctance, making them unlikely to consider private tuition for their children under normal circumstances.

Indecisive

Indecisive parents demonstrate inconsistency and uncertainty in their responses across different components of the scale. While they may acknowledge certain benefits of private tuition, doubts regarding feasibility and social influence prevent them from forming a clear decision. Their decision-making remains unstable and may fluctuate depending on situational or contextual factors.

References

- Abu-Shawish, R. K. (2023). Students' Perspectives on the Factors That Influence the Use of Private Tutoring Usage in Qatar. *Sage Open*, 13(4).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231210374>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (2005). The Influence of Attitudes on Behaviour. In D. Albarracín, B. T. Johnson, & M. Zanna (Eds.), *The Handbook of Attitudes*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 173-221.
- Ali, S., & Jha, S. K. (2013). Student's Institution Satisfaction Scale (ISBN: 978-938398-03-4). Agra: National Psychological Corporation.
- Armitage, C. J., & Conner, M. (2001). Efficacy of the theory of planned behaviour: A meta-analytic review. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 40(4), 471-499.
- ASSOCHAM (2013). Private coaching poaches mainstream education. Retrieved <http://assocham.org/newsdetail.php?id=4050>
- Baidya, S., Ray, S., & Sikdar, D.P. (2024). Parental Perception and Attitude towards Private Tuition: A Cross-Sectional Study among Daily Wage Earners. *Research Review International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 9(6), 279-288.
<https://doi.org/10.31305/rrijm.2024.v09.n06.034>
- Basu, J. (2014). Shadow Schooling Socio-Economic Analysis of the increase in the trend of Private Tuition in Government Schools.
https://www.academia.edu/6161520/Shadow_Schooling

- Berberoglu, G., & Tansel, A. (2014). Does private tutoring increase students' academic performance? Evidence from Turkey. MPRA Paper No. 57370, posted 17 July 2014. <http://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/57370/>
- Bray, M. (1999). The shadow education system: private tutoring and its implications for planners. Paris: IIEP-UNESCO.
- Bray, M. (2003). Adverse effects of private supplementary tutoring-Dimensions, implications, and government responses. IIEP Paris
- Bray, (2009). Confronting the Shadow Education System: What Government Policies for What Private Tutoring? Paris: IIEP-UNESCO.
- Bray, M. (2021). Shadow Education in Europe: Growing prevalence, underlying forces, and policy implications. *ECNU Review of education*, 4 (3), 442-475
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2096531119890142>
- Bray, M. & Lykins, C. (2012). Shadow Education Private Supplementary Tutoring and Its Implications for Policy Makers in Asia. CERC Monograph Series in Comparative and International Education and Development no. 9: Asian Development Bank.
- Buchmann, C., Condron, D. J., & Roscigno, V. J. (2010). Shadow education, American style: Test preparation, the SAT, and college enrollment. *Social Forces*, 89(2), 435–461.
- Byun, S.Y., & Park, H. (2012). The Academic Success of East Asian American Youth: The Role of Shadow Education. *Sociology of Education*, 85(1), 40-60.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0038040711417009>

- Chingtham, T. (2015). Necessary Evils of Private Tuition: A Case Study. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*. 5(2), 6-11. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-05220611>
- Choudhury, P.K., Gill, A.S., & Kumar, A. (2024). What drives demand for private tutoring in secondary education? Evidence from India. *Journal of Social and Economic Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40847-023-00291-8>
- Choudhury, P. K., Kumar, A., & Gill, A. S. (2021). Who all access private coaching in higher education and how much do they spend? Evidence from India. *Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy* 28(4), 1433–1455. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13547860.2021.1954302>
- Dang, H. & Rogers, F.H. (2008). How to Interpret the Growing Phenomenon of Private Tutoring: Human Capital Deepening, Inequality Increasing, or Waste of Resources?, Policy Research Working Paper 4530, Development Research Group, The World Bank, Washington DC.
- Davies, S. (2004). School choice by default? Understanding the demand for private tutoring in Canada. *American Journal of Education*, 110(3), 233–255.
- Dongre, A., & Tewary, V. (2015). Impact of private tutoring on learning levels. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 50(41), 72–80.
- Elbadawy, A., Assaad, R., Ahlburg, D., & Levison, D. (2007). Private and Group Tutoring in Egypt: Where is The Gender Inequality? Working Paper 0429 Economic Research Forum. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/erg/wpaper/0429.html>
- Field, A. (2013). *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS* (4th ed.). Sage Publications

- Goyal, Y. (2016, June 18). Shadow education. *The Indian Express*.
<https://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/shadow-education-private-coaching-kota-privatetuition-2859563/>
- Gupta, S. (2016, July 28). The business of private tutorials in India now a multi-billion industry. *Business World*. <http://www.businessworld.in/article/Business-Of-Private-Tutorials-In-India-Now-A-Multi-Billion-Dollar-Industry/28-07-2016-100972/>
- Jha, S.K. (2013). Assessment of the Three R Skills among Primary School Students. *The Primary Teacher*, 38 (3), 72-80.
<https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/publication/journalsandperiodicals/theprimaryteacher/PTJuly-Oct2013.pdf>
- Jha, S. K. (2023). The Three E's of Private Tuition in India: Expansion, Expenditure, and Effect. *Journal of Education* 203(2), 423-432.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00220574211032345>
- Jha, S.K. (2024). Chasing Shadows of Education Across the States in India: Mapping Its Policies and Practices at School Level. In Md. Bayezid Alam (Ed.) *Shadow Education in Asia: Policies and Practices* (pp. 214-233). IGI Global Publication,
<https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-2952-8.ch012>
- Jha, S.K. & Kumar, A. (2014). *Superstitious Belief Scale*. Agra: National Psychological Corporation.
- Kim, H. K. (2013). An analysis of the causes of shadow education in the era of the schooled society [PhD. Thesis]. The Pennsylvania State University.
https://etda.libraries.psu.edu/files/final_submissions/9089

- Kinyaduka, B.D. (2014). Private tutoring: A critical analysis of world experiences. *Merit Research Journal of Education and Review* 2(8), 135-140.
- Kumar, I., & Chowdhury, I.R. (2021). Shadow Education in India: Participation and Socioeconomic Determinants. *Journal of South Asian Development*, 16(2), 244-272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09731741211032472>
- Matsuoka, R. (2015). School socioeconomic compositional effect on shadow education participation: Evidence from Japan. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 36(2), 270–290.
- Madhu, S., & Bhattacharyya, D. (2018). A study on Parental attitudes towards Private Tuition at Senior Secondary level. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 6(1), 1490-1494.
- Mishra, A & Singh, P. (2022). Attitude, Subjective Norms, and Perceived Behavioural Control as Predictors of Entrepreneurial Intentions Among Engineering Students. *Prabandhan: Indian Journal of Management*, 15(5), 43-58. <https://doi.org/10.17010/pjom/2022/v15i5/169580>
- NSSO (2016). *Social consumption: Education, NSS 71st round* Government of India.
- Pallegedara, A., & Mottaleb, K.A. (2018). Patterns and determinants of private tutoring: The case of Bangladesh households. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 59, 43-50.
- Oyewusi, L. M., & Orolade, K. S. (2014). Private tutoring boom in Nigeria: An investigation into the emerging but controversial learning space. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 4(6), 271–274.

- Rocha, V., & Hamed, S. (2018). Parents' Perspectives on Paid Private Tutoring in the United Arab Emirates. UNESCO Regional Center for Educational Planning.
- Sengupta, I., & Ghosh, P. (2022). Intra-household Gender Disparity in Private Tuition: Evidence from West Bengal. *Indian Journal of Human Development*, 16(2), 352-366. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09737030221123178>
- Silova, I., & Bray, M. (2006). The hidden market place: Private tutoring in former socialist countries. In I. Silova, V. Būdiene, & M. Bray (Eds.), *Education in a hidden marketplace: Monitoring of private tutoring* (pp. 71–98). Open Society Institute.
- Singh, P., & Gupta, A. (2020). The influence of socio-economic status on educational decisions in India. *Asian Journal of Education*, 15(2), 101-117.
- Sharma, G.K. (2024). Unraveling the Shadow: Exploring the Growth and Implications of Private Supplementary Tutoring in India. In In Md. Bayezid Alam (Ed.) *Shadow Education in Asia: Policies and Practices* (pp. 181-213). IGI Global Publication, <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-2952-8.ch011>
- Snehi, N. (2010). Gender Equity in Private Tutorials: A Case Study of Delhi. *Review of Development and Change*, 15(2), 201-217.
- Sujatha, K. (2014). Private tuition in India: trends and issues. *Revue internationale d'éducation de Sèvres*. <https://ries.revues.org/3913>
- Wright, K.B. (2005). Researching Internet-Based Populations: Advantages and Disadvantages of Online Survey Research, Online Questionnaire Authoring Software Packages, and Web Survey Services. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 10(3), <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2005.tb00259.x>

Zhang, W., & Bray, M. (2016). Micro-neoliberalism in China: public-private interactions at the confluence of mainstream and shadow education. *Journal of Education Policy*, 32(1), 63–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680939.2016.1219769>

Pre-Print

**NEW SOLID WASTE
MANAGEMENT RULES 2026**

Four Stream segregation of Solid Waste at source

T. M. Regd. No. 564838
Copyright Regd. No. A-73259/2005 Dt. 13.5.05

NATIONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CORPORATION

UG-1, Nirmal Heights, Near Mental Hospital & Halwai Ki Bagichi, Agra-282007

• Email : info@npc-india.com

• 9457173567

• website : www.npcindia.com
(An ISO 9001 : 2015 Certified Company)

**Parental Decision-Making
Scale for
Private Tuition**

Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Jha

ISBN : 93-474-2490-0

9 789347 424908